

The Re-Discovered Tomb of Usermontu

TT 382 in Qurnet Murai

Sayed Mamdouh Soliman presents a preliminary report on the Supreme Council of Antiquities' rediscovery and study of tomb of Usermontu (TT 382), the First Prophet of Montu, Lord of Armant, located in the Southern part of Qurnet Murai hill in Thebes.

The Theban tomb TT 382 is located in Qurnet Murai among burials of other high-ranking officials, south of Sheikh Abd el Qurna. This hill was occupied by the end of the 18th Dynasty (c. 1550-1292 BCE) but was used mainly under Ramesside Period (c. 1292-1189 BCE). The Qurnet Murai necropolis contains 17 numbered tombs, many of which were inhabited by the Qurnawi people. Most of these numbered tombs are dated to the Ramesside Period, four date to the late 18th Dynasty, and one tomb, TT 380, dates to the Ptolemaic period (c. 305-30 BCE). Five tombs were covered under the modern buildings of Qurnet Murai, and the tomb of Usermontu was one of them. Four tombs in this area belonged to officials with ties to the cult of the god Montu.

In 2010, the Supreme Council of Antiquities started a cleaning project in Qurnet Murai after demolishing some modern houses in this area. The project began in the southern part of the hill, and one of the initial objectives was to uncover TT 382, because previous reports by Ahmed Fakhry and Bernard Bruyère in the 1930s noted its presence. However, when the tomb was relocated, it was inaccessible due to the area's occupation by modern houses. It was necessary to remove the house of Herajy, which was located above TT 382. The tomb was marked with a red brick wall, which was used as a mastaba in front of the house.

History of TT 382

TT 382 is located in the southern part of the Qurnet Murai hill and is oriented south-

west on the middle terrace of the mountain. Its east-west axis extends under the transverse hall of TT 271, which dates to the time of the king Ay (1323-1320 BCE), on the upper level. Until 12 years ago, the only remaining traces of the tomb were two articles and the red granite sarcophagus of Usermontu, which currently resides in The Metropolitan Museum of Art in New York (17.190.2042a-c). The tomb was presumably discovered in the late 19th or early 20th Century by the inhabitants of Qurnet Murai. Access to the tomb was initially through another tomb, TT 271, on the upper terrace.

In 1934, a report published by Bernard

Sarcophagus of Usermontu, c. 1279–1213 BCE, at the Metropolitan Museum of Art (17.190.2042a–c).

The tomb location in front of Herajy house before its demolishing in 2010.

Photo: Matjaz Kacicnik and Hassan Aglan

Photo and illustration showing the relation between TT 382 and TT271 on the upper level.

Bruyère presented a survey done by Maurice Alliot in Qurnet Marei. This paper mentioned that the owner of a house in Qurnet Murai reached another tomb through illegal digging with the help of other Qurna people and found a black granite top of a sarcophagus. As this sarcophagus was covered with sand and rocks that had fallen during the illegal digging, he could only read that the owner was a High Priest of Montu.

Yet, it was Ahmed Fakhry who was the first to mention the discovery of TT 382 in one of his reports: "The owner who built his house in front of one of the big tombs and he started illegal digging from inside at the north-east corner of the inhabited tomb, TT 271. Through a sloping passage in the rock, the robbers pushed their way until they reached the tomb of Usermontu, and they probably reached the burial chamber of the tomb from its back. When the Authorities heard the story, the

Top plan for TT 382 after its cleaning in 2018.

Illustration: Mohamed Abdelbast

house was searched, but no objects were found. As a result, a case was made against the house owner and an iron door installed for TT 382". A very brief description of the tomb was given by Fakhry in his 1936 report, which mentioned the name of the owner 'Usermontu' and his title as 'High Priest of Montu, Lord of Thebes'. While, in fact, the inscriptions in the tomb record his title as 'High Priest of Montu, Lord of Armant', which is the same title held by his father.

Tomb Owner's Titles and Family

Usermontu held multiple important titles, including High Priest of Montu, Lord of Armant, Great Steward, Overseer of the Cattle, Overseer of the Treasury, and Overseer of the Double Granary. The wife of Usermontu was previously known only with the title 'the great one of the harem of the god Montu Lord of Armant'. However, in the fourth scene on the upper register of the north wall of the long hall, she is mentioned with another title 'mistress of the house, Songstress of the God Thoth'. This is interesting because most Theban attestations of this title refer to Amun, rather than Thoth. His father was called Min-mose and was a High Priest of Montu, Lord of Armant as well as 'God's father of Montu, Lord of Armant'. His mother's name is lost, but textual remains mention that she held the title of the 'great one of the harem of the god Montu'.

Tomb Preservation and Architecture

After removing the modern house, the excavation started in the forecourt of the tomb. The top layers on the forecourt evidenced a flash flood, which contained a lot of Ptolemaic and Graeco-Roman pottery fragments. The stratigraphy indicates that the tomb most likely experienced two episodes of flash flooding. The tomb itself was full of debris, stones, and human remains. The latter were mixed with debris due to damage caused by the robbers looking for shafts in the transverse and longitudinal halls. Additionally, fallen plaster fragments from the walls and the ceiling of the transversal hall are mixed in with the debris. The human remains are distributed throughout the tomb, and no complete mummies were found. The majority of the material consists of isolated skeletal elements due to the extensive reuse of the tomb. Many

pottery fragments and sandstone blocks were found on the floor of the second passage, of which some belonged to the lintels and the jambs of the main entrance of the tomb.

The tomb has a traditional inverted T-shape design, consisting of a small entry passage that leads to a transverse hall, which is intersected by another passage leading to the longitudinal hall. At the end of the longitudinal hall, there is a chamber with a niche. At the end of the chamber's north wall, a sloping passage leads to the north. An unexcavated side chamber cut into the end of the first part of the passage opens to the east and faces the entrance of the burial chamber.

EES-funded Excavations during 2018

In 2018, I received the Centenary Award from the Egypt Exploration Society. These EES funds enabled all the surface features of the second entry passage and the longitudinal hall to be recorded and cleaned.

The transverse hall was cleared entirely of human remains covering the two sides of the hall. During the clearance of the transversal hall, more than one thousand painted plaster fragments that had fallen from the tomb walls were discovered mixed among the human remains. An initial investigation determined that most of the painted plaster fragments came primarily from the north-west and north-east walls of the transversal hall. A restoration team worked with the excavation team to remove the pieces by hand and photograph them for initial documentation, before placing them in temporary storage for future study. Despite the damaged condition, the fragments still show unique scenes and well-preserved colours. The completion of their research will provide more information about the themes within the tomb decoration.

The Decoration Program of TT 382

TT 382 was completely plastered, painted and decorated. The condition of the walls varies from one area to another. The surviving decoration is almost entirely from the long hall, rear chamber, and niche, whilst the plaster of the transversal hall has slipped entirely, except for small areas of the ceiling and lower corner of the chamber's north wall. In the antechamber, most of the plaster has remained on the tomb rock surface. However, the images are slightly unclear, as the paint was affected

Photo: Ayman Damarany

Photo: Sayed Soliman

Photo: Hazem Shared

by high temperatures resulting from using the fire inside the tomb. In contrast, the longitudinal hall paintings and scenes are in good condition. This differentiation of conservation is due to two main reasons. The first was natural disturbances, two episodes of flooding, which affected the state of the tomb paintings in the lower parts of the long hall, and the main reason for plaster falling off the transversal hall. The second reason is the long history of the reuse of the tomb, with the worst damage occurring during modern times. Tomb robbers used fire to light the tomb during their search for artefacts. These high temperatures affected

Photo of the left side of the Transversal hall after the rediscovery of the tomb in 2011, showing the fallen painted plaster fragments mixed with the human remains.

Photo showing Abo Goma collecting the coloured plaster fragments with great joy.

Samples of the plaster fragments from the transversal hall.

Photo: Matjaz Kacicnik

Photo of the decorated longitudinal hall of TT 382.

some painted areas and changed the original colours. This discolouration can be noticed clearly in the top part of the painted walls.

The ceiling of the transverse hall was divided into sections by long bands inscribed with hieroglyphs and patterns of flowers and geometric figures in different colours, of which small portions are still intact on the ceiling.

The wall scenes in the long hall are composed of four registers, two on each side. On the north wall, the upper register contains five scenes from the Book of the Dead Chapter 18, showing the journey of the deceased and his wife to the netherworld, where they are depicted repeatedly adoring different gods. The lower register contains scenes from Chapter 125 from the Book of the Dead, the judgment scene, and the negative confession. On the south wall, the upper register contains scenes from Chapter 146 of the Book of Dead, where the deceased and his wife are depicted repeatedly standing in adoration in front of the gates. The lower register is not in a good state of preservation, but a depiction of Usermontu's funeral procession can still be recognised. The plaster of the ceiling of the long hall is completely lost, and nothing remains of its

Photo showing Usermontu and his wife adoring the gods. BD 146, longitudinal hall, South wall, upper register.

decoration.

The rear chamber was fully decorated with offering scenes, but unfortunately, most of the scenes are no longer visible as a result of the use of fire. The upper wall frieze depicts Anubis sitting on the roof of a chapel with two vertical lines of hieroglyphic writing containing Usermontu's name and titles in front and behind the chapel, with three *khekeru* between each chapel.

A brief survey of the wall scenes in Usermontu's tomb suggests that it was built during the Ramesside Period. Cleaning the transverse hall revealed many plaster fragments, one bearing the cartouche of Rameses II as well as another plaster fragment which shows the face of a king. However, after complete clearance of the transversal hall, dating became more problematic due to the discovery of a plaster fragment depicting and naming the king Setnakht—founder of the Twentieth Dynasty (c. 1189–1077 BCE). The scene depicts him presenting offerings to the god Montu, Lord of Armant. Further research will have to clarify whether TT 382 was reused and if parts of its wall decoration were redecorated in the Twentieth Dynasty.

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Photo: Matjaz Kacicnik